

DAMAGE INITIATION AND ACCUMULATION IN METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Damage initiation and accumulation in particle reinforced metal matrix composites (PRMMC) have been determined separately by a combination of novel experimental techniques. By monitoring the acoustic emissions on straining, the damage initiation rate was found to be independent of the volume fraction of reinforcement. The percentage of particles that have failed at fracture is of the order of 10%. The sum of damage initiation and accumulation was found by x-ray microtomography. These showed a pronounced volume fraction effect on the void volume fraction at failure and the rate of void growth. The lower reinforcement volume fraction material has a higher void volume fraction at failure implying that void growth is more important there. Simple power law void growth laws are used for the two volume fractions of reinforcement to illustrate the effect of stress triaxiality on damage evolution.

1. INTRODUCTION

On straining, Particle-Reinforced Metal Matrix Composites (PRMMC) sustain damage by the nucleation and growth of internal voids. This simultaneous initiation of new damage and the accumulation of damage formed at lower strains manifests itself in the degradation of a number of the materials' mechanical properties such as stiffness and density. These changes, however, can be used to monitor the progression of the materials to failure and provide a tool to study their fracture. The properties chosen to define such damage parameters must in turn be sensitive to the fracture mechanism and be measurable at all strains to ultimate failure. It is also important to be able to separate the contributions from initiation and accumulation so that their relative importance may be known and, thus, appropriate measures can be taken to optimise the composite's properties.

Damage initiation in MMCs occurs at the reinforcing phase either by separation at the particle/matrix interface or by cracking of the reinforcement itself, forming a void. The sudden, localised change in stress levels on failure gives rise to the generation of transient elastic waves which propagate through the material and can be detected by transducers placed on the surface of the specimen. These are known as acoustic emissions (AE). Since the emissions are produced only when voids are formed, the monitoring of AE during straining gives an independent, quantitative measure of damage initiation.

The sum of damage accumulation and initiation has been studied by a number of workers by measuring bulk properties [1,2,3]. Problems arise when determining bulk physical or mechanical properties, for example, stiffness, if the deformation localises to a small region of the specimen. Displacements measured over these regions are not representative of the deformation, and moduli calculated from these measurements are invalid. These considerations, where the parameter is dependent on the specimen geometry, also restrict the use of other parameters (such as acoustic attenuation or scattering, electrical resistivity) to strains where there is uniform specimen deformation.

A candidate parameter which is independent of geometry is density. This has the advantage that the failure mechanism in PRMMCs is that of void nucleation and growth where density changes are expected. The technique will also provide information on the local matrix failure as well as the reinforcement failure. It has been shown that the ductility of PRMMCs is dominated by the onset of

flow localisation in the matrix phase which is itself controlled by the local matrix failure [4]. However, density measurements by weighing techniques during straining are difficult to perform experimentally, requiring the repeated interruption of the test whilst the specimen is removed and subsequently replaced in the loading rig [2]. Whilst the measurements themselves are not invalidated by the localisation of the deformation, it has been shown that by comparing densities at the fracture surface and in the gauge length, the damage concentrates in this region [5]. Thus, density measurements made over the entire gauge length lose their sensitivity and such global damage measurements at failure do not represent the local criterion for failure.

Many non-destructive evaluation techniques have been applied to damage characterisation in composites, but only non-destructive imaging methods using x-radiation offer the requisite combination of spatial resolution, the ability to examine specimens larger than 1cm^3 , very high sensitivity to changes in density or in elemental composition and relatively straightforward interpretation of complex structures. X-ray microtomography (XMT) is a miniaturised form of the well-established technique of computerised axial tomography used in medical diagnosis. Computed tomography records the projected image from a series of line projections of a cross-section of the object at different orientations (Figure 1). These projections are then combined via a reconstruction algorithm to produce a map of the linear absorption coefficient of the cross-section [6]. Thus, information on the size, shape and location of a feature within the material can be obtained with a spatial resolution of approximately $10\mu\text{m}$, allowing large features to be imaged directly. Damage accumulation in MMCs is by the growth of voids. Any reconstructed pixel in the image containing partial volumes of voids will have its absorption coefficient lowered by the fraction of the pixel occupied by the voids. This enables a local void volume fraction to be obtained at any part of the specimen at any strain once the absorption coefficient from an undeformed region is known. Thus, damage information can be generated even when the individual defects are below the imaging threshold.

Figure 1: Two projections of a single material consisting of two cylinders

The localisation of deformation, which invalidates other techniques, provides here the means for the study of the evolution of the damage. A failed tensile specimen which has necked contains a frozen strain history of the deformation process as regions near the fracture surface have undergone different strains. Thus, by simply taking tomographic slices progressively further from the fracture surface, the change in damage as a function of strain can be obtained. Additionally, since the technique measures the area of the slice, the true strain at each point can be evaluated. The critical levels of damage at failure and the rate of increase of damage with strain as a function of the microstructural variables will be determined. The local void volume fraction gives the sum of the damage initiation and accumulation.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The materials studied were composites of 5, 10 and 20% volume fraction of $30\mu\text{m}$ silicon carbide particles in a commercially-pure aluminium (Al-1070) matrix. This was fabricated by the powder metallurgy route of vacuum hot-pressing and extrusion at AEA Technology, Harwell Laboratories, UK, the details of which can be found elsewhere [7]. Specimens for tensile testing were turned and centrelessly ground.

Acoustic emissions were monitored during tensile tests to failure at a strain rate of $6.7 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. A Meccasonics 2.5MHz damped broadband piezoelectric transducer was held in contact with the end of the specimen by a spring within a specially designed tensile grip. This split grip was earthed to the mechanical testing machine and gave the specimen electrical and acoustic isolation. The triggering threshold of the peak detector was set independently to the ambient noise level. The data were recorded in two ways: the peak heights of emissions were fed through an A/D converter and these digital data stored on a microcomputer with the time of the event; simultaneous load/displacement and r.m.s. acoustic power were displayed on a chart recorder. The output was calibrated using a pulsed laser which allowed a one-to-one correspondence between digital data and diameter of cracked particles to be made, confirming that emissions were due to the failure of the particles alone.

In parallel, tensile tests to failure were performed at a strain rate of $3.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The failed specimens were examined by XMT (Figure 2). The x-ray generator was operated at 2.0 mA and 40kV with a silver target. A $10\mu\text{m}$ diameter Pt electron microscope aperture was positioned as close as possible to the target to maximize the x-ray beam intensity. A $60\mu\text{m}$ thick palladium filter was used to reduce the $\text{AgK}\beta$ radiation. The specimen was placed immediately behind the aperture on the kinematically designed rotation and translation stage [8]. A solid state Si(Li) detector and a single channel analyzer set to pass $\text{AgK}\alpha$ x-radiation with a 4% window was used to measure the transmitted intensity. Each projection was measured by recording the time to count 500 photons at each of 128 points separated by $15\mu\text{m}$. 251 projections at 1.434° angular intervals were measured for each section. Sections were taken at $50\mu\text{m}$ intervals along the gauge length from the fracture surface. The sections were reconstructed onto a 256×256 grid by a filtered back projection algorithm that did not incorporate any smoothing. A more complete description of this XMT system can be found elsewhere [9].

Figure 2: Experimental arrangement of XMT apparatus.

3. RESULTS

Acoustic emissions were detected from the onset of plastic deformation and continued throughout the entire plastic regime. The cumulative frequency of acoustic events for the three composites as a function of strain is shown in Figure 3. The rate of emissions and, hence, void nucleation, is approximately linear with strain for every system and increases with volume fraction of reinforcement. We normalise the number of emissions to the original number of particles to define a damage initiation parameter, D_i , such that

$$D_i(\epsilon) = \frac{n_f(\epsilon)}{n_i}, \quad (1)$$

where $n_f(\epsilon)$ = number of fractured particles at strain ϵ ,
 n_i = number of particles present initially.

n_i is calculated by assuming the particles are spheres of diameter $30\mu\text{m}$. Figure 4 shows $D_i(\epsilon)$ for the composites studied, where the data lie on one curve, irrespective of volume fraction of the reinforcing phase. The gradient of the line is $\approx 0.0045\%^{-1}$. The value of D_i at failure gives the macroscopic percentage of particles fractured during tensile straining. This is of the order of 10%.

Figure 3: Cumulative frequency of emissions as a function of strain.

Figure 4: Void nucleation damage as a function of strain.

Although in most cases individual voids could not be imaged by XMT, any pixel containing partial volumes of voids will have an absorption coefficient decreased by the fraction of the pixel occupied by the voids. To evaluate a void volume fraction from the variation in linear absorption coefficient, we have assumed that the mean absorption coefficient for a slice is equal to the sum of contributions from the integral composite and the voids. The value for the undeformed composite was measured from a slice through the threaded region of the specimen. Thus

$$\mu_m = (1-f) \mu_0 \quad (2)$$

where μ_m = mean absorption coefficient,
 f = void volume fraction,
 μ_0 = absorption coefficient for undeformed composite.

Using this definition, the plots of void volume fraction against strain for both composites are given in Figure 5. These give a higher void volume fraction at fracture in the 5% volume fraction composite (0.12 compared to 0.05 in the 20% volume fraction composite).

We now assume that the void volume fraction, f , satisfies a simple power law in strain. That is

$$f = A\epsilon^n, \quad (3)$$

where A and n are constants. Figure 6 shows the natural logarithm of the void volume fraction against the natural logarithm of the strain, giving n for the 5% volume fraction material as 2.1 and 4.9 for the 20% volume fraction material.

Figure 5: Void volume fraction as a function of true strain.

Figure 6. Ln(void volume fraction) as a function of ln(true strain).

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The results of Figure 3 show an approximately linear relation between the number of acoustic emission events and plastic strain. It is known that in this material the void nucleation and hence acoustic emission is associated with particle fracture [4]. Thus the proportion of fractured particles, as plotted in Figure 4, can be determined as a function of strain and is found to be independent of particle volume fraction. This insensitivity is surprising unless there is little interaction between the zones of stress relaxation around the reinforcing particles. The linear relation between particle fracture and strain is also unexpected if a Weibull formulation is assumed for the probability of particle fracture. A possible explanation is that the stress builds up in the particles with increasing strain with a power relation close to $1/m$, where m is the Weibull modulus. Work hardening curves have been measured in PRMMC which show a very flat form which may be consistent with this hypothesis [10]. However, further work is needed to explore the relations between far field strain, particle stress and fracture in PRMMC.

Consider the damage accumulation in terms of the increase in void volume fraction. The AE results in Figure 3 have shown that there is continuous void nucleation at a fixed rate with plastic strain. That is

$$\frac{dN}{d\epsilon} = \text{constant, or } N = M\epsilon \quad (4)$$

The increase in void volume at a strain ϵ_0 , $dV^v(\epsilon_0)$, for increment of strain $d\epsilon$ is

$$dV^v(\epsilon_0) = dN \times (\text{void volume change}) \\ = M d\epsilon (g(d\epsilon) \times V) \quad (5)$$

where V = void volume on nucleation,
 $g(\epsilon)$ = void growth law.

Hence, the total void volume at a strain ϵ_c is given by integration over all strains,

$$V^v(\epsilon_c) = \int_0^{\epsilon_c} MVg(\epsilon)d\epsilon = MV \int_0^{\epsilon_c} g(\epsilon)d\epsilon \quad (6)$$

We assumed a simple power law relating void volume fraction to strain. The experimental data gave the void volume fraction, f , to be proportional to the square of the strain for the 5% V_f PRMMC and to the fifth power of the strain for the 20% V_f material, implying $g(\epsilon)$ is proportional to ϵ and ϵ^4 respectively. It has been shown that the growth of a void formed between two halves of a fractured particle is constrained to the width of that particle until coalescence occurs. This implies that the void effectively grows in one dimension. Thus, in the 5% V_f material the void simply grows at the rate of the far-field strain rate, implying that the voids are independent of one another until high strains when there is large stress triaxiality due to necking which promotes void growth. This is shown in the upturn of the $\ln(f)$ against $\ln(\epsilon)$ plot at high strains. However in the 20% V_f material a high degree of stress triaxiality occurs at lower strains because of the large fraction of undeforming particles present. Thus, a much higher power growth law is observed throughout the deformation prior to void coalescence at fracture.

The characterisation of the mechanisms of void nucleation, growth and coalescence are key to the full understanding of the fracture behaviour of PRMMC. Here we have shown how it is possible to separate the measurement of the nucleation process from the total microstructural damage found prior to ultimate fracture of the composite by using acoustic emission monitoring. X-ray microtomography has also been used to provide a high degree of spatial resolution of the damage development away from the final plane of separation at fracture. Together the results show the importance of stress triaxiality in controlling the damage evolution in low matrix strength PRMMC.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank the Science and Engineering Research Council for funding under the rolling grant on metal matrix composites GR/F87660. One of us (PMM) also thanks the SERC for a post-doctoral Fellowship. Many thanks to Drs P. Anderson, G. Davis and J.C. Elliott at the London Hospital Medical College for performing the tomography experiments, Dr C.B. Scruby at the National NDT Centre, Harwell Laboratories for help with the acoustic emission experiments, and Dr J.H. Tweed and co-workers at AEA Technology, Harwell Laboratories, for providing the material.

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